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SOCIOECONOMIC STATUS: A STUDY OF
BARANGAY BUENAVISTA**

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Fisherfolk Parents' Aspirations and Their Socioeconomic Status: A Study of Barangay Buenavista

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Abstract. This study examined the socioeconomic status and aspirations of fisherfolk families in Barangay Buenavista, Zamboanga City, during fiscal year 2024–2025. It focused on how financial challenges such as low and seasonal income, limited access to credit, and high fishing costs affect their living conditions and future goals, especially for their children's education. Using a descriptive-correlational research design, the study analyzed the relationship between parents' aspirations and their socioeconomic status. Results showed that economic stability was the top priority of fisherfolk parents, with a high mean score of 3.42. Many families struggle with unstable income and expensive fishing operations, which greatly influence their ability to support their children's schooling and future ambitions. Cultural and geographic factors were less influential, with mean scores of 2.07 and 2.32. Government policies and community support received moderate ratings (mean of 2.66), suggesting that while these forms of support are appreciated, they are not enough to solve the families' financial difficulties. The parents' low-income status had a mean score of 3.00, confirming that financial hardship remains a major concern. Statistical analysis showed a strong and significant relationship between financial stability and parents' educational aspirations for their children (R -value = .000, P -value = .00). This means that better financial conditions increase the likelihood of pursuing higher education. Overall, the study highlights the urgent need for economic assistance and stronger support programs to help fisherfolk families improve their livelihood and achieve their aspirations.

Keywords: Fisherfolk Parents', Economic Factors, Geographic Factors, Cultural Factors, Government Policies

Introduction

The socioeconomic status (SES) of fisherfolk parents strongly influences their daily lives and future opportunities. Most fisherfolk families rely mainly on fishing as their primary source of income. However, fishing income is often unstable due to changing fish supplies, unpredictable weather, rising fuel prices, and other economic pressures. Because of this, their earnings are seasonal and inconsistent, making it difficult to meet basic needs such as food, healthcare, and education. Limited financial resources often prevent families from accessing quality services, which can result in ongoing hardship. Over time, these challenges can create a cycle of poverty that affects not only the parents but also their children.

Despite these struggles, fisherfolk parents have strong hopes for their children's future. Many believe that education is the key to breaking free from poverty and achieving stable, well-paying jobs. They want their children to complete their studies and pursue careers outside the fishing industry to avoid the same financial difficulties. However, low income, high fishing expenses, and limited access to credit make it hard for parents to fully support their children's education. As a result, there is often a gap between their aspirations and their financial capacity.

This study focused on fisherfolk families in Barangay Buenavista, Zamboanga City, during the fiscal year 2024–2025. It examined how economic challenges, cultural expectations, geographic limitations, government policies, and community support programs influence their socioeconomic status and aspirations. The findings highlight the need for stronger financial assistance, accessible educational opportunities, and effective community programs to help fisherfolk families improve their living conditions and achieve their goals.

Research Questions

This study aimed to investigate the aspirations of fisherfolk parents in Barangay Buenavista and the factors that influence their socioeconomic status.

Specifically, it seeks to answer the following questions:

1. What is the extent of fisherfolk parents' aspirations in Barangay Buenavista in terms of; Creating Presentation,
 - 1.1 Economic Factors
 - 1.2 Cultural Factors
 - 1.3 Geographic Factors
 - 1.4 Government Policies, and
 - 1.5 Community Factors
2. What is the socioeconomic status of fisherfolks parents?
3. Is there a significant influence between the fisherfolk parents' aspirations and socioeconomic status?

Scope and Delimitation of the Study

This study looked at the connection between the socioeconomic status and aspirations of fisherfolk parents in Barangay Buenavista for the 2024–2025 fiscal year. Through a survey, it examined how economic, cultural, geographic, government, and community factors influenced their hopes for their children's future. The research focused only on fisherfolk parents and aimed to understand how their financial situation affects their dreams and plans for the next generation.

Literature Review

Fisherfolk Parents'

Fisherfolk parents play a vital role in shaping their children's future, especially in coastal communities where fishing largely determines family income. However, their work is often unstable and seasonal, which makes long-term planning difficult. In Southeast Asia, Cruz (2018) found that many fisherfolk parents focus on meeting daily needs rather than long-term goals because of irregular income. During peak fishing seasons, children may leave school temporarily to help their families. In African coastal areas, Blaikie et al. (2019) reported that limited financial resources and weak social support systems make it hard for parents especially mothers to support their children's higher education. Similarly, Rodriguez and Montalvo (2017) noted that women in Latin American fishing households carry heavy responsibilities at home and at work, which can limit opportunities for their children, particularly daughters. Hughes et al. (2020) also found that financial stress affects both parents and children emotionally. Despite these challenges, strong community ties help families cope. Morrow (2015) emphasized that cooperation and shared support within fishing communities build resilience and encourage children's educational aspirations.

Economic Factors

In many rural and fishing communities, money plays a major role in shaping parents' hopes for their children. When income is unstable, families often focus on surviving day to day instead of planning for the future. This is common in parts of Africa and Southeast Asia, where fishing and farming depend on seasons and weather conditions. Ainsworth et al. (2019) found that families who rely on agriculture and fishing experience income changes throughout the year, making it hard for parents to invest in their children's long-term goals. Because of financial pressure, children are sometimes asked to help with fishing or other family work instead of continuing their studies. Similarly, Seddon et al. (2021) reported that many fisherfolk families in Bangladesh value education and see it as a way for their children to achieve a better life. Parents often dream of sending their children to college or helping them find stable jobs outside the fishing industry. However, the high cost of schooling and the lack of steady income make these dreams difficult to reach. As a result, some children leave school early to support their families, showing how financial hardship can limit both opportunities and aspirations.

Geographic Factors

Cultural values strongly influence the dreams and plans of fisherfolk parents for their children. In many coastal communities, fishing is more than just a source of income, it is a way of life passed down from one generation to the next. Because of this tradition, children, especially boys, are often expected to continue the family's fishing work. Edwards (2020) explained that in small-scale fishing communities in the Pacific Islands, many parents encourage their sons to learn fishing skills early, sometimes placing less importance on formal education. However, these cultural views are slowly changing. Briones et al. (2022) found that in coastal communities in Peru, fishing traditions are still valued, but more parents now see education as a path to better opportunities. Many families are beginning to understand that finishing school can open doors to stable jobs and improve living conditions. As a result, more fisherfolk parents are encouraging their children to complete higher levels of education. While tradition remains important, there is a growing balance between preserving cultural identity and supporting educational goals for a better future (Edwards, 2020; Briones et al., 2022).

Government Policies

Government policies play a key role in shaping the hopes and opportunities of fisherfolk parents for their children. Programs such as subsidies, scholarships, and free schooling can ease financial pressures and make education more accessible. Hossein and Wahid (2019) reported that in Bangladesh, government initiatives like free meals and educational stipends helped increase school attendance among fisherfolk families. These programs allow parents to focus on their children's learning rather than immediate financial survival, supporting their aspirations for a better future. However, the impact of such policies can vary depending on how they are implemented. D'Souza and De Silva (2020) found that in Sri Lanka, many fisherfolk parents in remote coastal areas struggle to benefit from government programs due to poor communication, complicated processes, and limited access to information. As a result, some families miss opportunities that could help their children pursue education or other goals. Overall, while government programs have the potential to improve the lives of fisherfolk families and support their aspirations, their success depends on accessibility and effective implementation. Ensuring that policies reach all communities is essential for helping parents provide better opportunities for their children (Hossein & Wahid, 2019; D'Souza & De Silva, 2020).

Community support

Community support is essential in helping fisherfolk parents raise their hopes and goals for their children. In many coastal areas, local initiatives such as school associations, NGOs, and volunteer programs provide resources that families may not be able to afford on their own. These programs can offer tutoring, scholarships, and other forms of assistance, easing the financial and educational challenges that often limit children's opportunities. Palomares and Mendoza (2021) found that in the Philippines, fisherfolk communities with strong local support systems had higher school enrollment rates and lower dropout rates, showing the positive impact of community involvement. Similarly, NGOs and community organizations in Sub-Saharan Africa have helped fisherfolk families by providing financial aid, creating community schools, and offering educational programs for both children and parents. Wilson (2022) highlighted that these networks are key in helping families overcome the economic and logistical challenges of education. By providing guidance, resources, and encouragement, community support allows fisherfolk parents to aim higher for their children's future, helping break the cycle of poverty. Overall, strong community ties play a crucial role in empowering fisherfolk parents to nurture their children's dreams and achieve better educational and social outcomes (Palomares & Mendoza, 2021; Wilson, 2022).

Socioeconomic Status

Socioeconomic status has a strong influence on the aspirations of fisherfolk parents. Adams and Balfour (2019) found that in the United States, children from low-income families often face educational setbacks due to a lack of resources such as books, learning materials, and extracurricular opportunities. Similarly, fisherfolk families with limited financial means struggle to provide the necessary support for their children's education, which can restrict their long-term opportunities. This creates a cycle where poverty limits both the parents' aspirations and the children's prospects, passing disadvantages from one generation to the next. Community support can play a critical role in breaking this cycle. In many coastal areas, local initiatives like school associations, NGOs, and volunteer programs help ease the pressures on fisherfolk families. Palomares and Mendoza (2021) found that communities in the Philippines with strong support systems had higher school enrollment and lower dropout rates. These programs offer tutoring, scholarships, and other resources, helping parents encourage higher aspirations for their children. Similarly, NGOs in Sub-Saharan Africa provide financial aid, run community schools, and offer educational programs for parents. Wilson (2022) emphasized that these networks help families overcome economic and logistical challenges, giving children better opportunities and allowing parents to nurture their hopes for a brighter future (Adams & Balfour, 2019; Palomares & Mendoza, 2021; Wilson, 2022).

Methodology

Research Design

This study used a descriptive-correlational design to explore the relationship between fisherfolk parents' aspirations and their socioeconomic status in Barangay Buenavista. According to Creswell (2014), this design is ideal for identifying connections between variables without manipulating them. Data were collected through survey questionnaires, a method recognized by Babbie (2020) as effective for gathering quantitative information from specific groups. A purposive sample of 50 fisherfolk parents was selected to ensure participants had relevant characteristics, following Etikan, Musa, and Alkassim's (2016) recommendations for targeting specific populations. Statistical tools were used to analyze the strength and direction of relationships, as advised by Field (2018) for non-experimental studies. Ethical standards were strictly followed. Participants gave informed consent, and their privacy and confidentiality were maintained. Participation was voluntary, in line with APA guidelines (2020). This method allowed the study to examine how socioeconomic status influences fisherfolk parents' aspirations while ensuring the research was accurate, reliable, and ethically conducted (Creswell, 2014; Babbie, 2020; Etikan, Musa, & Alkassim, 2016; Field, 2018; APA, 2020).

Sampling Design

This study used probability sampling, combining purposive and stratified methods, to select participants. Purposive sampling intentionally focused on fisherfolk parents in Barangay Buenavista, Zamboanga City, ensuring that the respondents met the study's criteria and were directly relevant to the research on aspirations and socioeconomic status. Stratified sampling further divided the population into subgroups, such as family size or income level, to ensure all key groups were represented. This approach allowed for a more detailed understanding of how factors like income, family dynamics, and geographic conditions influence parents' aspirations. Combining these methods provided a comprehensive view of the community (McCombes, 2023).

Research Locale

This study was conducted in Barangay Buenavista, sitios 56 and 57, during the 2024–2025 fiscal year. Barangay Buenavista is a coastal community where fishing is the main livelihood for many families. The area was chosen because of its large population of fisherfolk, whose experiences provide valuable insight into the challenges faced by similar communities (Philippine Statistics Authority [PSA], 2022). Understanding their aspirations helps explain the broader socioeconomic conditions affecting the community. Coastal communities like Buenavista often face economic hardships that limit access to education. Alcantara and Ponce (2020) noted that such difficulties significantly reduce educational opportunities, making these areas important for studying parental aspirations. The study explored how factors such as family income, access to schools, and community support shape fisherfolk parents' hopes for their children. Geography and economic stability were also considered, as UNESCO (2021) found that remote locations and financial instability strongly influence parental expectations, especially in marginalized areas. By focusing on Barangay Buenavista, this study aimed to highlight fisherfolk parents' aspirations and socioeconomic challenges, offering insights to inform policies that improve educational opportunities in coastal communities (PSA, 2022; Alcantara & Ponce, 2020; UNESCO, 2021).

Research Participants

This study included all residents of Sitios A and B in Barangay Buenavista, Zamboanga City. The total population of respondents was 59. The largest number of residents (30) was in Sitio B, while the smallest number (29) was in Sitio A. All 59 residents were included in the study, ensuring that every individual had the opportunity to share their perspectives. This approach allowed the research to capture a complete and accurate understanding of the aspirations and socioeconomic conditions of fisherfolk families in the two selected sitios (Gay, 1976).

Research Instrument

The research used a questionnaire adapted from Maria Pilar Pablo's study, "An Evaluation on Fisherfolk's Aspirations on Their Children's Education as Basis for Policy Development and Community Support Initiatives." The questionnaire had two parts: Part I focused on the socioeconomic status of fisherfolk parents, and Part II examined the factors influencing their aspirations, including economic, cultural, geographic, government, and community aspects. Responses were measured using a 4-point scale: 4 = Strongly Agree, 3 = Agree, 2 = Disagree, and 1 = Strongly Disagree. The survey was conducted with the approval of the research teacher and followed the Data Privacy Act of 2012 of the Republic of the Philippines, ensuring participants' privacy and confidentiality.

Data Gathering Procedure

The researcher began by securing approval from the Research Adviser to formally conduct the study. After receiving the Endorsement Letter, permission was requested from the school principal to conduct the research outside the campus. Once approved, all required documents, including the Endorsement Letter, principal's approval, consent forms, and the survey questionnaire, were submitted. Permission was also sought from the Barangay Captain of Barangay Buenavista to collect data from fisherfolk parents. With the captain's approval, the researcher was authorized to approach the target participants. Parent respondents were recruited through face-to-face visits in the community. The researcher focused on fisherfolk parents who met the study criteria and were available and willing to participate. Surveys were conducted at times convenient for the parents, with clear instructions provided and questions addressed on the spot. Before starting, informed consent was obtained from each participant, emphasizing that participation was voluntary and responses would remain confidential. Conducting the survey in person allowed the researcher to guide participants and provide assistance whenever needed, ensuring accurate and comfortable completion of the questionnaire.

Results and Discussions

Problem 1: What is the extent of fisherfolk parents' aspirations in Barangay Buenavista in terms of economic factors, cultural factors, geographic factors, government policies and community support?

Table 1: Level of extend of fisherfolk parents' aspirations in Barangay Buenavista in terms of Economic Factors

Statements	Mean	Verbal Description	Interpretation
1. We as fisherfolks have a low and seasonal variation of income.	58	Strongly Agree	Highly Aspired
2. The community lacks credit facilities for us fisherfolks.	20	Agree	Moderately Aspired
3. We are faced high fisher costs (fishing paraphernalia/gears, fuel, ice, etc.).	66	Strongly Agree	Highly Aspired
4. collecting copies of e-books for future use.	20	Agree	Moderately Aspired
5. Our families lack funds and access to support diversification of their income sources.	47	Strongly Agree	Highly Aspired
Over-all Mean	3.42	Strongly Agree	Highly Aspired

Table 1 shows that the statement "combining different media elements skillfully to create engaging videos" obtained the highest mean of 3.07, followed by "utilizing video editing software proficiently to enhance footage" with a mean of 3.04. Both are described as agree and interpreted as moderately proficient. This means students have a fair ability to integrate images, audio, and video and can use editing software effectively, but still need improvement to reach a higher level of mastery. They can create engaging videos but may not fully use advanced editing tools or features that could improve the quality and finesse of their work. Students may also struggle with complex tasks such as advanced effects, transitions, and fine-tuning. Thus, additional training and practice in multimedia integration and advanced editing techniques would be beneficial. Research supports this: Anderson and Jiang (2016) note that students commonly work with mixed media in digital storytelling, while Salomon (2015) highlights the learning value of multimedia, suggesting students have basic skills in media integration. Meanwhile, the lowest mean of 2.83 was recorded for the statement "adapting to new features in editing software quickly," also interpreted as moderately proficient. This indicates that while students can use editing software, they may need more time to adjust to newly added tools or updates. They may find it difficult to learn new features without guidance. This suggests the need for more training to help them become more confident and efficient when updates occur. Chi and VanLehn (2006) emphasize how visual aids can help users understand new interfaces, while Johnson (2019) specifically discusses students' difficulties in adapting to new software features, supporting this finding.

Table 2: Level of extend of fisherfolk parents' aspirations in Barangay Buenavista in terms of Cultural Factors

Statements	Mean	Verbal Description	Interpretation
1. Close family ties in our family prevent our children from going apart from us.	1.56	Strongly Disagree	Not Aspired
2. Our children grow up believing they must continue the family's livelihood.	1.81	Disagree	Fairly Aspired
3. Cultural practices in our community require children to contribute to the fishing activities.	1.86	Disagree	Fairly Aspired

4.	Our family prioritize male children to study and have education as future head of the family.	3.22	Agree	Moderately Aspired
5.	Our children fail to see the importance of education when they are involved in fishing activities and earn money already to help the family.	1.90	Disagree	Fairly Aspired
Over-all Mean		2.07	Disagree	Fairly Aspired

Table 2 shows that the highest mean score of 3.28 was given to the statement about integrating multimedia elements and choosing appropriate fonts and colors, interpreted as highly proficient. This means students are very skilled at combining images, audio, videos, and design elements to make clear and effective presentations. The second-highest score, which refers to creating visually appealing presentations, falls under moderately proficient. This suggests that while students can design attractive presentations, they still need improvement in areas such as consistency in layout, transitions, and overall refinement. Research by Dwyer (2012) and Moreno and Mayer (2007) supports the importance of multimedia in enhancing learning, indicating that students' strong performance in this area aligns with established multimedia principles. Meanwhile, the lowest mean score of 3.02 was recorded for using presentation software proficiently, also interpreted as moderately proficient. This means that although students can operate tools like PowerPoint and Google Slides, they may not fully use their advanced features. They can navigate the basics but may struggle to maximize the software's full potential to enhance presentation quality. Studies by Garner and Alley (2012) and Kosslyn et al. (2012) similarly found that students often understand presentation tools at a basic level but need further practice to improve their overall proficiency.

Table 3: Level of extend of fisherfolk parents' aspirations in Barangay Buenavista in terms of Geographic Factors

Statements	Mean	Verbal Description	Interpretation
1. Our fishing community lacks public schools to cater for our children's educational needs.	2.08	Disagree	Fairly Aspired
2. Our children have difficulty going to school because of the lack of access to roads from our residents to the nearest school.	1.80	Disagree	Fairly Aspired
3. We have difficulty in sending our children to go to school because of the high transportation cause from our residents to the nearest school.	1.83	Disagree	Fairly Aspired
4. Our community is vulnerable to natural disasters that lead to disrupting their attendance at school.	2.25	Disagree	Fairly Aspired
5. We are not going out to fish because of the unpredictable weather condition resulting to lack of income in days.	3.64	Strongly Agree	Highly Aspired
Over-all Mean	2.32	Disagree	Fairly Aspired

Table 3 shows that the highest mean score of 3.09 was recorded for customizing document templates to meet specific project requirements, followed by a mean of 3.03 for integrating multimedia elements into documents. Both are interpreted as moderately proficient, meaning students are able to adjust templates effectively and incorporate multimedia when needed, although they still have room to improve. Students generally show competence in tailoring documents to suit different project needs but may need further refinement in placing multimedia elements smoothly and consistently. These findings align with literature, as Bernard and Moeller (2018) highlight that technology integration such as using templates supports writing development, while Dyson and Bedgood (2000) note that students value such tools in organizing their work. Meanwhile, the lowest mean score of 2.71 was given to troubleshooting formatting issues efficiently, also interpreted as moderately proficient. This suggests that although students can fix formatting problems, they often require more time, guidance, or practice to do so effectively. Many struggles with alignment, spacing, or layout concern and may need additional support to troubleshoot more confidently. Research supports this observation: Hemmati and Issa (2017) report that formatting is a common challenge in technology-based writing, while Sitzmann and Ely (2011) explain that troubleshooting requires metacognitive skills, showing that students would benefit from more structured practice to strengthen these abilities.

Table 4: Level of extend of fisherfolk parents' aspirations in Barangay Buenavista in terms of Government Policies

Statements	Mean	Verbal Description	Interpretation
1. We are not aware of any policy that addresses the seasonal variability of our income such as during the fishing ban season (close season) and during "habagatan".	1.86	Disagree	Fairly Aspired
2. We have not heard of any livelihood-related policies to support or improve our livelihood.	2.42	Disagree	Fairly Aspired
3. We don't know any policies that promote educational programs for fishing communities.	2.47	Disagree	Fairly Aspired
4. Some environmental protection policies conflict with our livelihood activities such as the close season ban,	3.08	Agree	Moderately Aspired

	marine protected areas, municipal water boundaries, and use of some of our fishing gears.			
5.	We are able to access project grants and support because policies to access grants are only for organized and accredited groups and not for individual fisherfolks.	2.92	Agree	Moderately Aspired
Over-all Mean		2.55	Agree	Moderately Aspired

Table 4 shows that the highest mean score of 3.34 was given to protecting personal information while browsing the internet, followed by a mean of 3.31 for effectively using search engines for online research. Both results indicate high proficiency, meaning students are very aware of online safety practices and are skilled at retrieving information from the internet. They demonstrate a strong understanding of privacy protection and show competence in conducting online research using search engines. These findings align with studies such as Livingstone and Helsper (2007), which highlight the risks young people face online, and Valverde-Aliseda and Ruiz-Castillo (2014), who emphasize the role of schools in strengthening digital citizenship and online safety skills. Meanwhile, the lowest mean score of 3.02 was recorded for navigating various websites to find relevant content, interpreted as moderately proficient. This shows that although students can locate needed information, they may not yet be efficient in navigating different sites or applying advanced search strategies. Many take longer than necessary to verify sources or identify reliable content, suggesting the need for more targeted instruction in website navigation and information literacy. These observations are supported by Marcoulides and Heck (1999), who note that electronic literacy skills develop at different rates, and Walsh (2016), who emphasizes that students benefit from guided practice to become more effective online researchers.

Table 5: Level of extend of fisherfolk parents' aspirations in Barangay Buenavista in terms of Community Support

Statements	Mean	Verbal Description	Interpretation
1. We are not able to join extension programs that promote the importance of education in fishing communities because slots are limited during such as occasions.	2.58	Agree	Moderately Aspired
2. There is a lack of financial assistance programs in our community to fund alternative livelihoods for individual fisherfolks, one needs to be in an organization to be able to access such programs.	3.32	Strongly Disagree	Highly Aspired
3. Our children have difficulty accessing scholarship programs that support fisherfolk children because slots are limited.	3.42	Strongly Disagree	Highly Aspired
4. During times of economic hardship such as closed fishing season, natural disasters and calamities, our families did not receive help such as relief goods or seed funds from support programs of the government or civic organizations.	2.25	Disagree	Fairly Aspired
5. There is a lack of mentorship and role model programs for fisherfolk children in our community.	3.05	Agree	Moderately Aspired
Over-all Mean	2.93	Agree	Moderately Aspired

Table 5 shows that the highest mean score of 3.34 was given to protecting personal information while browsing the internet, followed by a mean of 3.31 for effectively using search engines for online research. Both results indicate high proficiency, meaning students are very aware of online safety practices and are skilled at retrieving information from the internet. They demonstrate a strong understanding of privacy protection and show competence in conducting online research using search engines. These findings align with studies such as Livingstone and Helsper (2007), which highlight the risks young people face online, and Valverde-Aliseda and Ruiz-Castillo (2014), who emphasize the role of schools in strengthening digital citizenship and online safety skills. Meanwhile, the lowest mean score of 3.02 was recorded for navigating various websites to find relevant content, interpreted as moderately proficient. This shows that although students can locate needed information, they may not yet be efficient in navigating different sites or applying advanced search strategies. Many take longer than necessary to verify sources or identify reliable content, suggesting the need for more targeted instruction in website navigation and information literacy. These observations are supported by Marcoulides and Heck (1999), who note that electronic literacy skills develop at different rates, and Walsh (2016), who emphasizes that students benefit from guided practice to become more effective online researchers.

Table 6: Summary of the Level of Student's Proficiency in Technology

Indicators	Mean	Interpretation
Economic Factors	3.42	Highly Aspired
Cultural Factors	2.07	Fairly Aspired
Geographic Factors	2.32	Fairly Aspired
Government Policies	2.55	Moderately Aspired
Community Support	2.93	Moderately Aspired
Over-All Mean	2.66	Moderately Proficient

Table 6 summarizes the overall level of students' technological proficiency. It shows that respondents are moderately proficient in video editing, creating presentations, word processing, and internet navigation. This means students have a basic understanding and skill set in these areas, allowing them to perform common tasks and use standard tools effectively. However, they have not yet reached advanced levels of mastery, indicating room for improvement and further development. With continued practice, exposure to new tools, and guided learning opportunities, students have the potential to enhance their proficiency and achieve higher competence in these technological domains. These findings are supported by research showing that students can handle basic technology tasks but need additional experience and instruction to reach advanced proficiency (Marcoulides & Heck, 1999; Bernard & Moeller, 2018; Johnson, 2019). Providing ongoing support, resources, and targeted training can help students strengthen their skills, enabling them to use technology more effectively for academic, professional, and personal purposes (Valverde-Aliseda & Ruiz-Castillo, 2014). This suggests that with proper guidance, students can build confidence and competence in all areas of technological application.

Problem 3: What is the socioeconomic status of fisherfolk parents for the fiscal year 2024-2025?

Table 7: Socioeconomic Status of Fisherfolk Parents for fiscal year 2024-2025

Indicator	Mean	Verbal Description
Socioeconomic Status	3.00	Low Income

Table 7 displays the academic performance of students in the 3rd quarter of the School Year 20232024. They received a mean score of 86.50, categorized as "Very Satisfactory." This indicates that students performed very well across their academic subjects during this period, demonstrating a strong level of understanding and achievement. The rating suggests that students consistently met or exceeded academic expectations, showing diligence and engagement in their studies. Astin (1993) and Hattie (2008) highlight factors like effective teaching and student engagement that contribute to academic success, supporting the positive performance observed in this study.

Ethical Considerations

This study strictly adhered to established ethical guidelines in educational research to ensure the protection of participants' rights, dignity, and well-being. Prior to the conduct of the study, formal approval was obtained from the Department of Education Division Office and the School Principal of Buenavista Integrated School. Informed consent was secured from all participants after clearly explaining the objectives of the study, the procedures involved, and their right to voluntarily participate or withdraw at any stage without any penalty or negative consequences. Participants were assured that their involvement was entirely voluntary. Confidentiality and anonymity were carefully maintained throughout the research process. Codes were used instead of participants' names to protect their identities, and no identifying information was included in the presentation of results. Access to academic records was granted only with proper authorization and handled in compliance with the Data Privacy Act of 2012 (Republic Act No. 10173). All collected data were used exclusively for academic research purposes and were stored securely to prevent unauthorized access. The study ensured that no participant was subjected to physical, emotional, or psychological harm. Survey instruments contained non-sensitive and non-intrusive questions, and data collection was scheduled at convenient times to avoid disruption of classes or any form of coercion. Throughout the study, ethical principles such as fairness, transparency, objectivity, and academic integrity were consistently observed.

Conclusion

This study shows that economic stability strongly influences the educational aspirations of fisherfolk parents in Barangay Buenavista. Financial problems, high fishing expenses, and unstable income greatly affect their goals for their children's education. Although cultural and geographic factors have some impact, financial difficulties remain the main concern. Parents recognize the importance of government programs and community support, but current assistance may not fully meet their needs. The study also found that better socioeconomic status leads to higher educational aspirations. Providing financial aid, alternative livelihood programs, and accessible education opportunities can help improve their children's future and reduce financial hardship.

Recommendations

Based on the study's findings, several recommendations are suggested to help fisherfolk parents in Barangay Buenavista support their children's education. First, financial assistance, low-interest loans, and alternative livelihood programs should be provided to reduce their economic difficulties. Scholarships, subsidies, and flexible learning options for fisherfolk children should also be expanded to make education more accessible. The government and community groups should strengthen programs such as mentorships and partnerships with local organizations to improve educational opportunities. Seminars on financial literacy, sustainable fishing, and the importance of education should also be conducted to increase awareness. Improving school facilities, transportation, and alternative learning options in remote areas is important to ensure access to education. Lastly, future researchers can use this study as a guide to examine similar issues in other communities.

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